

Conductive-hydrophobic coating on gas diffusion layer for enhanced proton exchange membrane fuel cell performance

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01. Introduction

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2. Challenges in Balancing Conductivity and Hydrophobicity in GDLs
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 - morphology, wettability, electrical conductivity, mechanical properties
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01. Introduction

1. Background of PEMFC and GDL
 2. Challenges in Balancing Conductivity and Hydrophobicity in GDLs
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Background of PEMFC and GDL

❖ PEMFC (Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell)

- **Electric energy and water (H₂O)** are generated via the **electrochemical reaction** between hydrogen (H₂) and oxygen (O₂).
- Due to **fast startup** and **low operating temperature (80–120 °C)**, PEMFCs are gaining attention in mobility applications.
- A PEMFC unit cell consists of (1) **Bipolar Plates**, (2) **Gas Diffusion Layers**, (3) **Membrane**, and (4) **Catalyst Layers**.

Electrochemical Reactions in PEMFC

Hydrogen oxidation reaction in Anode :

Oxygen reduction reaction in Cathode :

Overall Cell Reaction :
$$\text{H}_2 + 0.5\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}$$

Figure. Schematic image of PEMFC unit cell

Background of PEMFC and GDL

❖ GDL (Gas Diffusion Layer)

- GDL consists of GDB (Gas Diffusion Backing layer) coated with MPL (Micro Porous Layer).
 - ✓ GDL serves 1) uniform diffusion of reactant gases, 2) conduction of generated electrons and heat, 3) removal pathway for produced water.
- GDB : Carbon paper composed of carbon fiber layers is typically used, providing structural support to GDL
- MPL : Mainly composed of carbon black-based slurry; it reduces contact resistance with catalyst layer and prevents catalyst loss.

Figure. Illustration of gas diffusion layer

Figure. Images of GDB and MPL

Background of PEMFC and GDL

❖ Voltage losses in PEMFC

- During operation, PEMFCs exhibit **lower voltages than the theoretical value due to various losses.**
- These losses are typically categorized by the current density regions in which they have the greatest impact.
- Minimizing these losses requires **improving the material properties and performance of individual cell components.**

Figure. Various types of losses that occur during PEMFC operation

Table. Classification of major losses in PEMFC

Loss type	Loss mechanism
Fuel crossover loss	Losses caused by hydrogen diffusing through the membrane without reacting, reducing efficiency and open circuit voltage.
Activation loss	Losses caused by the activation energy barrier of the electrochemical reactions, particularly due to the slow kinetics of the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR).
Ohmic loss	Losses caused by resistance to ion flow in the membrane and electron flow in cell components, reducing cell voltage.
Mass transport loss	Losses caused by insufficient gas supply or water accumulation that blocks the pores of the gas diffusion layer, limiting reactant transport at high current densities.

Background of PEMFC and GDL

❖ Hydrophobic coating on GDB (Gas Diffusion Backing layer)

- Commercial carbon paper based GDBs are coated with **hydrophobic** agents such as **fluoropolymers, primarily PTFE**.
- This treatment prevents **water condensation and pore blockage**, thereby reducing **mass transport loss** in PEMFC.
- ✓ However, **fluoropolymers are electrically insulating** and significantly reduce the **through-plane electrical conductivity** of the GDB.

Figure. PTFE coating process of commercial GDB

Figure. Surface morphology of carbon paper before and after PTFE coating

^[2]Energy Convers. Manag. 2017, 154, 191-202

Figure. Reduction in through-plane electrical conductivity of GDL due to PTFE coating

^[3]IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng. 2017, 154, 191-202

❖ Studies on enhancing electrical conductivity of GDLs

- Various approaches have been used to enhance GDL conductivity via **structure, materials, and coatings**.
- **Metal-based GDLs and conductive coatings** still require **hydrophobic coatings for water management**, which **offset conductivity gains**.
- ✓ Therefore, it is essential to address the **fundamental issue of conductivity loss caused by hydrophobic coatings themselves**.

Figure. (a) Metal-based GDL, (b) Graphene-oxide coated GDL, (c) Cu fiber felt GDL

Research objectives

❖ Conductive and highly-hydrophobic coating on GDB for enhanced PEMFC performance

- **CNT/PTFE conductive-hydrophobic nanocomposite coating** on carbon paper (CP-GDBs)
 - Enhanced electrical conductivity, lower contact resistance, PTFE coating-level hydrophobicity, and improved PEMFC performance
 - Analysis of **GDB and GDL property variations according to CNT/PTFE ratio** in the coating
 - Characterization: SEM, contact angle, conductivity, compressibility, and cell performance testing
- **New coating improves conductivity over PTFE, contributing to PEMFC performance enhancement**

**Enhanced PEMFC power
(at RH 50%)**

02. Materials and Experiments

1. CNT/PTFE coated GDBs (CP-GDBs) and MPL coated CP-GDBs (CP-GDLs)
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CNT/PTFE-coated GDBs (CP-GDBs)

❖ Fabrication process of CNT/PTFE-coated GDBs (CP-GDBs)

Figure. Schematic illustration of fabrication of CP-GDBs

CNT/PTFE-coated GDLs (CP-GDLs)

❖ MPL coated CP-GDLs (CP-GDLs)

Figure. Schematic illustration of fabrication of CP-GDLs

03. Results and discussion

- 1. Characterization of CNT/PTFE nanocomposite**
 - 2. Characterization of CP-GDBs**
 - 3. Characterization of CP-GDLs**
 - 4. PEMFC unit cell performance**
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Characterization of CNT/PTFE nanocomposite

❖ Dispersion of CNT/PTFE Nanocomposite (C_{xx}P_{yy})

- To evaluate the dispersion of the CNT/PTFE nanocomposite, a film was formed by removing the water from the dispersion.
- No noticeable agglomeration of CNT or PTFE** was observed at the microscale.
- The small variation in electrical conductivity of the film** also indicated **uniform dispersion** of the nanocomposite.

Figure. Microstructure images by CNT/PTFE nanocomposite

Figure. Electrical conductivity of CNT/PTFE nanocomposite film

Characterization of CP-GDBs

❖ Surface morphology of CP-GDBs (C_{xx}P_{yy}B)

- SEM images reveal **CNT/PTFE nanocomposite microstructures** forming **film-like layers between carbon fibers**.
- As **CNT ratio in the nanocomposite increases**, **denser CNT networks** are formed while **PTFE content decreases**.
- **No CNT agglomeration** observed at the microscale, indicating **uniform dispersion of the nanocomposite**.

Figure. Magnified region (example)

Figure. Microstructure images by CNT/PTFE composition in nanocomposite

Characterization of CP-GDBs

❖ Hydrophobicity of CP-GDBs (CxxPyyB)

- **CNT/PTFE coating** imparted hydrophobicity **comparable to that of conventional PTFE-coated GDB (C0P100B, P-GDB)**, with a contact angle around 140°.
- **C90P10B exhibited hydrophobicity similar to pristine carbon paper** due to the **low PTFE content in the coating**.

Figure. Contact angle of CP-GDBs according to CNT-to-PTFE ratio in the nanocomposite

Figure. Water droplet images during contact angle measurement

Characterization of CP-GDBs

❖ Electrical conductivity of CP-GDBs (C_{xx}P_{yy}B) in TP* and IP** directions

- TP electrical conductivity was significantly improved by CNT/PTFE coating compared to conventional PTFE-coated GDB (P-GDB).
 - Increased from 4.85 S/cm (P-GDB) to 6.98 S/cm (C90P10B), representing a 44% enhancement.
- IP electrical conductivity remained nearly constant, regardless of the coating composition.

TP*: Through-plane
 IP**: In-plane

Figure. (a) TP and (b) IP electrical conductivity according to CNT-to-PTFE ratio of the coating

Characterization of CP-GDBs

IP*: In-plane

TP**: Through-plane

❖ Cause of electrical conductivity trends in CP-GDBs (CxxPyyB) in TP* and IP** directions

- TP direction : **In P-GDB (C0P100B), insulating PTFE blocks point contacts** between carbon fiber layers, **while CNT/PTFE coatings form additional inter-fiber conductive paths**, enhancing TP electrical conductivity.
- IP direction : **IP electrical conductivity is governed by continuous carbon fibers**, so coating has minimal effect.

Figure. (a) Cross-sectional SEM images of P-GDB and CP-GDBs, (b) surface SEM images of P-GDB and CP-GDBs

Characterization of CP-GDBs

❖ Mechanical properties of CP-GDBs (CxxPyyB)

- Compressive properties were evaluated for various CNT-to-PTFE ratios in the coating.
- As the proportion of PTFE (serving as a binder of GDB) decreased, **compressibility increased** and **stiffness decreased**.
- Mechanical property trend: **P-GDB > C01P99B ≅ C10P90B ≅ C25P75B ≅ C50P50B > C90P10B**

Figure. (a) Compression test setup and specimen dimensions, (b) compressibility by CNT-to-PTFE ratio in the coating, and (c) tangent modulus at 0.125 strain

Characterization of CP-GDLs

❖ Reduced contact resistance between CP-GDBs and MPL (in CP-GDLs, CxxPyyL)

- CP-GDBs exhibited **more than 50% lower contact resistance with MPL** compared to P-GDB.
- ✓ The **3D conductive CNT network** in the CNT/PTFE coating of CP-GDBs **entangles with the MPL**, increasing the conductive interface.
- **Contact resistance (R_{cont}) between CP-GDBs and MPL** was indirectly **estimated as $R_{GDL} - R_{GDB} = R_{cont} + R_{MPL}$** .
 - Since MPL was coated with the same composition and thickness, R_{MPL} was assumed to be constant.

Figure. Contact resistance between CP-GDBs and MPL in CP-GDLs

PEMFC unit cell performance

❖ Fuel cell performance (I-V, I-P curve) evaluation: relative humidity(RH) 50% and 100% conditions

- Under both low and high humidity conditions, **CP-GDLs showed superior performance compared to P-GDL (C0P100L).**
- **Performance increased with higher CNT-to-PTFE ratio in the coating**, reaching up to a 26% improvement.
 - **CNT/PTFE coating enhanced the electrical conductivity** of the GDB, leading to **reduced cell ohmic loss.**
- Despite higher conductivity, **C90P10L exhibited lower performance to C50P50L** due to its **relatively lower hydrophobicity.**

Figure. (a) Device setup for fuel cell performance test; I-V and I-P curves with CP-GDLs applied as cathode GDL, (b) Performance curves at RH 50%, and (c) performance curves at RH 100%. (I-V curve: dotted line, I-P curve: solid line)

04. Conclusion

Conclusion

❖ Conductive-hydrophobic coating of GDB via CNT/PTFE

- Conclusion

- CNT/PTFE conductive-hydrophobic coating on GDB:
 - ✓ Enhanced electrical conductivity
 - ✓ Improved unit cell performance (reduced ohmic loss)
 - ✓ Provided hydrophobicity
 - ✓ Maintained compressive stiffness
- Property variation by CNT/PTFE ratio
 - ✓ GDB properties are tunable according to the CNT-to-PTFE ratio in the coating.
- Optimal composition by condition
 - ✓ Under general operating conditions, C50P50 is optimal (balanced properties).
 - ✓ Under low-humidity conditions, C90P10 is optimal due to maximized conductivity.

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Thank you

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